

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Overview of proposed definitions for exposure and clinical markers.

Marker type	Exposure	Effect	
Definitions		Antecedent (pre-disease)	Incident (disease)
Confirmation & monitoring	<p>Exposure marker - confirms an exposure.</p> <p>Exposure monitoring - measured serially for evidence of exposure over time.</p>	N/A	<p>Clinical diagnosis – confirms presence of a medical disease.</p> <p>Clinical monitoring - measured serially for assessing status of a medical disease over time.</p>
Response and safety	<p>Exposure response – confirms a biological response to an exposure i.e., indirect exposure marker.</p> <p>Exposure safety - measured before or after an exposure to indicate an (adverse) response i.e. includes indirect exposure response marker.</p>	N/A	<p>Treatment response – confirms a biological response to an intervention in patients who have the disease i.e., pharmacodynamic marker.</p> <p>Treatment safety - measured before or after an intervention to indicate an (adverse) response in patients who have the disease i.e., includes indirect treatment response marker.</p>
Risk & prediction	<p>Exposure risk - likelihood to experience an exposure without intervention.</p> <p>Exposure prediction – likelihood to experience an exposure following intervention i.e., risk to be exposed if environment is altered.</p>	<p>Clinical susceptibility – likelihood to develop medical disease based upon genetic factors.</p> <p>Clinical vulnerability – likelihood to develop medical disease based upon genetic factors plus exposures.</p> <p>Prevention prediction - likelihood to develop medical disease following intervention i.e., risk to develop disease if exposures are altered.</p>	<p>Clinical prognosis - likelihood of recurrence or progression of medical disease in patients who have the disease without intervention.</p> <p>Therapeutic prediction - likelihood of recurrence or progression of medical disease in patients who have the disease following intervention.</p>

Definitions adapted from:

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